

Software Processes for NASA

Takeaways from the breakout discussions

Policy and Processes Retrospective

We are going to breakout into smaller groups for a retrospective on smaller groups. Those online will be randomly assigned a room.

Agenda for each breakout group:

1. Introductions (5 minutes)
2. Identify a leader
3. Take 6 minutes to write down some answers to the questions.
4. Discuss! Share your thoughts and experiences. Ask questions. Add user stories or feature requests under opportunities.
5. In the last five minutes, identify two main takeaways to share with the group. They could be questions for the wider group, experiences, next steps, or things to discuss further.

Questions

- What is working well for NASA software policy and processes?
- What processes need improving? And how?
- What opportunities are there ?

Breakout #2

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=/?share_link_id=482962262149](https://miro.com/app/board/uXjVKLR74SY=/?share_link_id=482962262149)

First takeaway: I hope the next time I go through the release process, it is simpler and easier than the first time.

Streamlined process hopefully better.

Second takeaway: Get clarification of releasing code and publications via SRRS vs STRIVES (current and future state).

508 compliance, handling of Licenses, replacement of proprietary components of software, ...: FAQ and How-Tos should be assembled.

Breakout #3

First takeaway:

TOPS has been an outstanding success, as has the onboarding of cloud resources and capabilities to enable NASA projects/personnel.

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Second takeaway:

- Consider establishing software CoP's that enable community collaboration and awareness of software and emerging technologies to be evaluated/used. Facilitate exchange of ideas.
- Issue due to lack of consolidated licenses across NASA and inability to leverage common resources. High agency costs to acquire necessary software (e.g. Atlassian products, Anaconda workbench, HPE workbench, etc.)

Breakout #5

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First takeaway:

Legacy software brings particular challenges to the release process.

Second takeaway:

Increased Training and Awareness is critical to better our communal efforts in Software Processes.

A Centralized repository of resources, where different agencies share their methods

Breakout #6

In-person

Breakout #6

In-person

First takeaway:

The top level policies (SPD-41a) and the NPR workbooks set good priorities and examples, but there is a lot of friction at the process level slowing down and disincentivizing open source release.

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Second takeaway

There is an opportunity to improve these processes by defining metrics around software release, automating standard forms (like the JIRA example we saw this morning), and leveraging LLMs to assist in preparing forms and asking questions about NPRs.

Breakout #7

Tracking SW (NTRs/Case Number) is what works well within the NASA Software policy and processes.

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Process is thorough for going through the requirements as reviews are conducted (for managing large projects); for smaller scientific projects - scripts/papers/studies, process may need refinement for small class missions - fast track review.

Breakout #8

First takeaway:

Software release process is daunting and overwhelming, hard to figure out what process is applicable to our projects.

Examples would be helpful, starting with the simplest case.

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Second takeaway:

Demo on the software release process to various stakeholders would be useful on learning how it is being done.

Breakout #A

First takeaway:

The vision of open source is in movement and this is what we want, but are we ready? Do we have the infrastructure? Who pays for the time and effort that this takes if the software is free?

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Second takeaway

DoD has compliance infrastructure (i.e. software factory) akin to test driven development to check for compliance of policies. Can NASA create a similar factory?

Breakout #B (onsite group 2)

First takeaway:

Mandating open source, open data, open science makes for easier science, opportunity to move from OSS to community building, open processes and collaborations.

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Second takeaway:

Sustainment money for software and for cyber-compliance needs more program support and funding.

Breakout #B (onsite group)

universal one™

Easel Pad
30 Sheets
25 in x 30 in

UNV35603

What went well | Needs improvement | Opportunities

Mandating
Open source
Makes easier
in my lab

Cloud documents

Sustaining
money for
software

Mismatch between
Agile and waterfall

moving from OSS
to community
building, open
processes, collaborations

Identify which
kinds of projects
lead then series to
agile, cultural's diff.

Open Data
open Science

cloud data lake
more efficient
data access

cyber-compliance
needs more
program support
and funding

Legal & software
engineering
requirements are
still stifling for
science projects

Macro waterfall,
Micro agile

Open science is allowing
New technology to be
used because data
must be shared

Streamlined
on ramping of ~~OSS~~
future
three compliance
procedures

Breakout #C

Take-Aways

1. We need to bridge the gap between science & software engineering & Open science communities
⇒ collaboration
2. Improving awareness, within SRA & Policy makers of Open Science

Breakout #C

universal.

Unruled • 30 Sheets

What's Working Well

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Breakout #D

(in person breakout group #4)

First takeaway:

Lots of (seeming?) duplication across different silos that haven't been socialized:

How to improve: Possibly this workshop helps! But common tool sharing mechanism?

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Second takeaway

Raise the importance of software open source product lines with SMD and tie to mission AOs to require NASA open source product lines.

Presenter: David Aronchick

Breakout #E

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First takeaway:

Going Well: Flow down allows for standardization and best practices across SMD functional areas.

Second takeaway

Opportunities: Updates to policies are addressing many gaps. Flow down to processes should align to close gaps in requirements across the cross-functional mission directorates (ie SMD, OCIO, OP, OGC)

Breakout #E.1

(in person 5)

First takeaway:

[Room for improvement] Still functionally in the same place we were 5-10 years ago; we need alignment in policies and processes across NASA (SPD-41a, NPRs, SRA, Legal) to enable open source.

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Second takeaway:

[Opportunity] Build connections / collaborations between what NASA does internally and externally in open source communities / other institutions; cross-pollination of ideas in open-source software.

Breakout #E.1

(in person 5)

https://miro.com/app/board/uXjVKLR_C CQ=?share link id=188233043186

Breakout #G

(In-person group 7)

First takeaway:

The SRA process (SRS) needs to be sped up and improved for different types of software (e.g. all open source).

More clear guidance on contributing to open source code, and providing an avenue for authorship for contributors.

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Second takeaway:

Reducing silos is critical. More frequent communication across the division is needed (even within centers).

More communication between developers, scientists, and the open science community is needed.

Breakout #H

First takeaway:

Good opportunity for more help in software development.

Examples: training, groups to help people through process (kudos GSFC Software Improvement group, Ames SRA)

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Second takeaway:

Moving from legacy code to translating to open source language